

Floral characters of CMS lines under two environments. Bangalore, India. 1991 DS and WS.

CMS line	Anther length (mm)		Anther breadth (mm)		Anther size (mm ²)		Stigma length (mm)		Stigma breadth (mm)		Stigma size (mm ²)		Style length (mm)		Pollen sterility (%)		Anthesis duration (min)	
	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS
V20 A	2.30	1.50	0.45	0.32	0.92	0.48	1.66	2.11	0.56	0.41	1.86	1.73	0.53	0.69	100.0	99.8	273	285
IR54752A	2.21	1.83	0.65	0.40	1.46	0.73	1.52	1.69	0.60	0.43	1.82	1.45	0.84	0.86	98.8	100.0	238	250
IMA	2.19	1.63	0.64	0.33	1.40	0.54	1.33	1.62	0.43	0.37	1.14	1.20	0.83	0.65	2.8	37.0	250	205
Mangala A	1.97	2.13	0.42	0.41	0.83	0.87	1.25	1.46	0.42	0.33	1.05	0.96	0.55	0.79	4.5	13.8	205	195
Pushpa A	2.40	1.76	0.41	0.38	0.98	0.67	1.61	1.50	0.42	0.31	1.35	0.93	0.55	1.00	1.5	17.0	211	185
PMS1 A	1.90	1.78	0.39	0.35	0.74	0.62	1.36	1.46	0.43	0.31	1.17	0.91	0.63	0.63	100.0	69.0	256	260
PMS2 A	1.84	1.34	0.39	0.33	0.72	0.48	1.36	1.27	0.43	0.31	1.17	0.79	0.92	0.95	98.5	98.0	251	260
PMS3 A	1.98	1.74	0.37	0.30	0.74	0.52	1.50	1.33	0.55	0.33	1.65	0.88	0.69	0.66	100.0	100.0	284	290
PMS4 A	1.75	1.36	0.35	0.34	0.63	0.63	1.40	1.65	0.44	0.36	1.23	1.19	0.72	0.77	98.2	74.0	255	285
PMS5 A	2.02	1.73	0.34	0.38	0.69	0.66	1.36	1.45	0.44	0.33	1.20	0.96	0.76	0.71	96.5	100.0	251	260
PMS6 A	1.99	1.70	0.30	0.29	0.60	0.49	1.43	1.33	0.43	0.33	1.23	0.88	0.73	0.82	88.6	100.0	208	218
PMS7 A	2.37	1.91	0.43	0.33	1.01	0.63	1.55	1.45	0.54	0.33	1.67	0.96	0.72	0.90	98.0	99.2	256	260
PMS8 A	1.96	1.69	0.37	0.26	0.73	0.44	1.58	1.37	0.47	0.33	1.49	0.90	0.74	0.86	99.3	98.9	246	265
PMS9 A	2.23	1.89	0.45	0.33	1.00	0.62	1.58	1.35	0.53	0.37	1.67	0.97	0.80	0.61	99.0	100.0	285	290
PMS10 A	1.85	1.89	0.36	0.37	0.67	0.62	1.52	1.57	0.53	0.37	1.61	1.16	0.62	0.65	97.0	100.0	257	265
Mean	2.05	1.76	0.43	0.34	0.87	0.60	1.47	1.50	0.48	0.35	1.42	1.06	0.71	0.77	78.84	80.45	248.49	251.63
Range	0.64	0.79	0.35	0.15	0.86	0.43	0.41	0.84	0.18	0.12	0.81	0.94	0.39	0.39	98.5	86.2	80.0	105.0
CV (%)	9.39	10.52	23.68	12.12	29.94	18.78	8.20	13.82	13.00	10.43	19.17	23.81	16.26	16.18	49.96	39.68	9.88	13.76
SE (m)	0.05	0.05	0.025	0.011	0.067	0.03	0.03	0.054	0.028	0.009	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03	10.17	8.22	6.34	8.93

between opening of the first spikelet in the main panicle in the morning and closing of all spikelets in that panicle.

Genotypes performed very differently under the two environments (see table). In general, the mean values for anther length, anther breadth, anther size, stigma breadth, and stigma size were greater in DS than in WS, while mean values for stigma length and pollen sterility were

greater in WS than in DS. No difference was observed between the environments for anthesis duration. Anthesis, however, started earlier (0900 h) in DS than in WS (1100 h).

Variability (indicated by range and coefficient of variation) for anther breadth, anther size, stigma breadth, and pollen sterility was higher in DS than in WS; for anther length, stigma length,

stigma size, style length, and anthesis duration, variability was higher in WS than in DS. Expression of floral traits influencing outcrossing was generally better in DS than in WS.

Results suggest that it is advantaged to produce hybrid rice seed during DS because more floral traits are better expressed than during WS. ■

Restorers and maintainers for MS 577 A and wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility system

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Ninety-six rice genotypes were crossed with six cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines possessing cytoplasmic male sterility system of MS 577 A and 24 genotypes with four wild abortive (WA)-type CMS lines, resulting in 252 F₁s with 577 A cytoplasm and 39 F₁s with WA cytoplasm. Based on spikelet fertility of these hybrids, genotypes were classified as restorers (>80%), partial restorers

(10-80%), and maintainers (<10%).

None of the 96 genotypes completely restored the fertility of 577 A. IR36, IR13146-45, IET7191, Karna, Milyang 54, and Nucleoriza however, were found to be partial restorers.

Of the 18 IRRI genotypes evaluated, 10 were identified as restorers for WA CMS lines (IR8, IR36, IR60, IRI3146-45, IR15324-13, IR20226-24, IR21543-2-1-22, IR27280, IR22810-60, and IR31916-9), 6 as partial restorers, and 1 as a maintainer (IR21916-128). Among other genotypes, 3 were identified as restorers (Cornell culture, ARC11353, and RP101-3-129), 2 as partial restorers, and 1 as a maintainer (local variety CTH1). ■

Yield potential

Performance of anaerobically direct seeded rice plants in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Most farmers in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam practice direct seeding. Improved rice cultivars are used, but they were selected for use in the transplanting system. Introducing cultivars suitable for direct seeding may benefit farmers. We conducted this study to identify desirable traits for high-yielding direct seeded rice